

THE USE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN ORTHODONTICS

Abstract

The application of artificial intelligence (AI) in orthodontics is very diverse and ranges from the identification of anatomical and pathological structures of the human dentition to support complex decision-making in orthodontic treatment planning. The purpose of this work was to analyze current views on the use of artificial intelligence techniques and models in orthodontics based on a literature review. The scientific publications of various scientometric databases (PubMed, Scopus, Google Scholar and Web of Science) over the past 5 years were processed. Artificial intelligence is one of the most promising tools due to its high accuracy and efficiency. Practicing dentists will be able to use it as an additional tool to reduce their workload. However, this requires close cooperation of commercial AI products with the scientific community, further research, including randomized clinical trials, to test and integrate this concept in dental practice.

Keywords: dentistry, diagnostics, machine learning, cephalometry.

Introduction

Orthodontic diagnostics is a complex process that combines various information obtained from the patient's facial and occlusal parameters, taking into account their individual needs. Artificial intelligence tools are used to make the diagnostic process more accurate and efficient. In orthodontics, its use has increased significantly in recent years, which is reflected in the exponential increase in the number of scientific publications on the integration of artificial intelligence into everyday clinical practice [1; 2].

Artificial intelligence (AI) is the ability of computer hardware to perform tasks that usually require human intelligence. In many cases, AI can be seen as a valuable tool whose algorithms help dentists and clinicians analyze data from multiple sources of information (multimodal data). These algorithms learn to see, process and understand the world in the same way as the human brain does, using a computational model called a convolutional neural network (CNN) to characterize and describe objects.

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Materials and methods

To achieve this goal, scientific publications of various scientometric databases (PubMed, Scopus, Google Scholar and Web of Science) were processed over the past 5 years.

Results and discussion

Orthodontic treatment planning is usually based on the clinical experience and practical skills of orthodontists. Since each clinical case is unique for each individual patient, treatment should be planned and discussed jointly by both parties. In orthodontics, AI is used to analyze the structure of the facial skeleton and identify anatomical landmarks [1], analyze X-rays and 3D scans, determine bone age, and plan and predict treatment outcomes [2]. These AI skills significantly

improve communication between patients and dentists, often eliminating the need for many clinical and laboratory processes.

and the results of such studies are much more accurate than those analyzed by humans [3].

The traditional and most difficult method of orthodontic diagnosis is phallometric analysis [1]. This type of radiographic examination was introduced by Broadbent B.H. back in 1931, but still remains the cornerstone of orthodontic treatment planning [4]. The first step in the analysis of cephalometric images is the identification of anatomical landmarks, on the basis of which geometric estimates can be made in the form of angles, distances and ratios, which allows the analysis of the human skull in different planes [5].

Before the use of artificial intelligence, geometric constructions and measurements were facilitated only by software solutions, but the identification of landmarks remained a routine task for a practicing physician [6]. Although manual identification remains the most commonly used method, the transition to artificial intelligence analysis avoids three-way procedures and minimizes systematic and random subjective errors. Today, various researchers have been able to automate this lengthy and error-prone process using AI algorithms [7; 8].

Yu H.J. and colleagues (2020) positively evaluated a CNN-related system, the sensitivity, specificity and accuracy of which reached more than 90% in the vertical and sagittal diagnosis of the skeleton [9]. Regarding the placement of anatomical landmarks, the use of artificial intelligence has shown an encouraging accuracy of their location in the range from 88.43 % to 92.00 %, depending on the clinical case [10; 11].

Most studies that investigate the use of artificial intelligence for automated cephalometric X-ray analysis evaluate the accuracy of their artificial intelligence based on the metric deviation between the benchmarks set by the artificial intelligence and the human gold standard. In this context, Schwendicke F. et al. (2021) conducted a meta-analysis that analyzed the accuracy of automatic landmark detection by different researchers. The authors demonstrated that most of the included

studies were able to identify landmarks within the metric tolerance limit of 2 mm [12].

Artificial intelligence tools with machine and deep learning demonstrated high accuracy in the calculation of cephalometric data, but they still require an orthodontist to additionally check the position of each landmark after automatic identification. Errors in landmark identification, rather than direct measurement of values, are still a significant source of analysis inaccuracy. This accuracy of landmark recognition from two- or three-dimensional images would be the key to automating the diagnostic procedure [14].

Assessment of growth potential and determination of the time of the initial growth spurt are of great importance for the correction of dysgnathia in children and adolescents [15]. The growth dynamics in adolescence varies greatly, so the assessment of chronological age alone is not sufficient to assess the degree of growth of a child [16]. Skeletal age, in turn, is much more suitable for individual growth assessment, which can be determined radiologically by growth-related changes in the wrist bones or vertebral bodies. This method is also known as the Cervical Vertebral Maturation (CVM) method. The analysis of both methods correlates significantly with each other [17]. Unlike X-rays of the wrist, the assessment of skeletal age based on the maturation of vertebral bodies has the advantage of not requiring additional

radiation exposure of the patient, as this assessment is performed on teleradiographs, which are in any case part of orthodontic diagnostics.

The CVM method is based on the morphological change of the C2-C4 vertebral bodies. Based on the analysis, six stages of skeletal maturity are distinguished [17]. The correct determination of the degree of skeletal maturity using this method is difficult. There is a high probability of errors due to individual anatomical features of patients. To eliminate the problem and objectify the determination of skeletal age, approaches to automate this process using AI have been developed [15]. The results of the study are quite different. According to Kok N. and co-authors (2019), they found a moderate coincidence of 58 % to 71 % between the predictions of CVM stages of artificial intelligence and the human gold standard [17]. Seo H. et al. (2021) were able to demonstrate high prediction accuracy for different AI algorithms, which was more than 90 % [18].

Estimating the age of individuals plays an important role not only in dentistry, but is also a cross-cutting issue in the context of forensic medicine. Thus, Guo Y.C. and co-authors (2021) collected 10,257 orthopantomograms and derived linear logistic regression models for each age threshold of 14, 16, and 18 years [19]. The method is based on the analysis of the left lower eight permanent teeth or a single third molar. After training the end-to-end CNN that classified the dental age, the results show that compared to manual methods (92.5%, 91.3%, and 91.8% for age thresholds of 14, 16, and 18 years, respectively), end-to-end CNN models perform better (95.9%, 95.4%, and 92.3% for age thresholds of 14, 16, and 18 years, respectively). This work proves that CNN models can outperform human

analysis skills in age classification, and the characteristics and age parameters determined by machine learning may differ from those analyzed by humans and be more accurate.

In orthodontic diagnostics, modern AI algorithms can also be used to determine the treatment plan [20]. One such example is the decision “for” or “against” tooth extraction for orthodontic reasons. Due to a variety of clinical, radiological, and even socio-cultural factors, decisions about orthodontic extraction remain complex. It is difficult to make the “ideal” choice in the best interest of the patient, as it also depends on the personal training, experience and philosophy of the practitioner [21; 22].

In recent years, several approaches have been developed to automate and objectify this complex process [21]. Different AI algorithms have been trained on a large amount of patient data, which included a selection of clinical data, radiological results, model parameters, and the corresponding expert opinion of the pros and cons of orthodontic extraction. The first studies showed promising results with a “correct” prediction of 80% to 94% as to whether extraction is required [21]. Important orthodontic parameters, such as the degree of crowding, position of the front teeth, inclination and occlusion, and lip closure, were analyzed by AI algorithms, which significantly influenced the decision to extract teeth.

Real A.D. et al. (2022) showed that AI algorithms can predict extraction decisions particularly reliably when radiological data and model parameters are used together as a diagnostic basis [23].

Jung S.K. et al. (2016) proposed a model for assessing the need for tooth extraction for orthodontic reasons.

using lateral cephalometric radiographs [24]. In addition, some studies have shown the extent to which artificial intelligence algorithms can additionally predict the ideal extraction scheme. For example, a combination of first and second premolar extractions in different quadrants. The correct prediction of the extraction model was presented in about 84 % of cases [24].

Jung S.K. et al. (2016) also showed that artificial intelligence expert systems with neural network machine learning can be useful in orthodontics based on lateral cephalograms of 156 patients [22]. For their work, they created 5 groups of treatment plans: no extraction, extraction of the first premolar of the upper and lower jaw, extraction of the second premolar of the upper and lower jaw, extraction of the first premolar of the upper and lower jaw, and only extraction of the first premolar of the upper jaw. After the training, the model had a 93% success rate for diagnosing extraction versus non-extraction, and 84% for analyzing the detailed diagnosis of different extraction patterns.

For general practitioners, Thanathornwong B. (2018) developed a system for assessing the need for orthodontic treatment of patients in the period of permanent occlusion [25]. A Bayesian network was chosen as the main model, which gave encouraging results and showed high accuracy in classifying patients into groups that need and do not need orthodontic treatment.

Another area of artificial intelligence application is orthognathic surgery [22]. The importance of this solution is relevant in cases where it is impossible to achieve adequate occlusion with orthodontic appliances, or when the patient's main complaints cannot be eliminated by orthodontic treatment alone. Therefore, irreversible procedures, such as tooth extraction, should not be performed until orthognathic surgery can be confidently ruled out [26]. Such decisions may also differ between practitioners due to differences in experience and different perspectives on the clinical situation. Since there are no standardized criteria for making decisions about the need for orthognathic surgery, there are approaches that try to support clinicians with AI algorithms [27].

Choi H.I. et al. (2019) proposed an artificial intelligence model to determine whether surgery is necessary when using lateral cephalometric radiographs. The success rate of the model was 96 % for diagnosing the surgical/non-surgical decision and 91 % for determining the type of future surgery and the decision to extract the tooth [28]. Kim Y.H. et al. (2021) used various convolutional neural networks as artificial intelligence algorithms that achieved 91% to 94% accuracy in predictions [26].

Similarly, Shin W. et al. (2021) and Lin G. et al. (2021) concluded with 95.4% and 87.4% accuracy, respectively, that a deep learning program can be used to determine the need for orthognathic surgery. The latter publication also determined that it is possible to predict the future need for surgical intervention to correct sagittal skeletal discrepancy in patients after cheilo- and uranostaphyloplasty at the age of 6 years [27; 29].

Photometry is widely used as an auxiliary method of diagnosis and subsequent treatment in orthodontics. Artificial intelligence tools have been proposed to assess photometric parameters after treatment [30; 31]. In the study by Jeong S.H. and co-authors (2020), 822 frontal and lateral photographs of the face were used to test and analyze a deep

were used to test and analyze a deep learning model and further diagnose dentofacial dysmorphism [30]. The sample was evaluated by 5 experienced clinicians and distributed according to the need for orthognathic surgery. The CNN algorithm showed an accuracy of 89.3% in predicting the need for orthognathic surgery using facial photographs. This is a valuable new approach that shows that artificial intelligence can be used to determine the need for orthognathic surgery, but additional training with other diagnostic data is needed to improve this tool.

Along with the analysis of the photographic protocol, an important part of the analysis of patient data for orthodontic diagnosis and treatment planning is dental models, which have undergone significant technological changes. Today, not only classical plaster impressions are used, but also digitally scanned impressions and full intraoral scanning [32]. The analysis of radiographs and images taken by intraoral scanners can be used for diagnosis and planning of orthodontic treatment. This eliminates the need for laboratory manipulations, such as taking analog impressions of patients

and casting models. The results of digital diagnostics are often much more accurate [33; 34].

The main task of such planning of orthodontic treatment is the segmentation and classification of teeth on digital models. Cui Z. et al. (2021) proposed several artificial intelligence algorithms for automatic segmentation of teeth on digital models scanned by a 3D intraoral scanner [35]. Cui Z. and co-authors (2022) also succeeded in segmenting teeth using cone beam computed tomography [36]. In addition to tooth segmentation, the researchers also segmented an alveolar cyst, the efficiency of which surpassed the work of radiologists.

Today, there is a growing interest in the use of AI for digital planning of aligners and fixation of braces. Using precise 3D scans and virtual models, aligners can be easily printed and manufactured according to a unique treatment strategy. Since a huge amount of data is processed, an algorithm is developed that determines the pressure and the way the patient's teeth should be braced, as well as the pressure points specific to that tooth or group of teeth. Aligners made using artificial intelligence shorten the treatment time, and make the process more accurate, simpler, and more predictable [1]. However, at present, digital adjustments are performed almost exclusively on digital dental models, which does not allow to assess the critical position of the roots of the teeth in the bone. Importantly, tooth movement, which may seem simple in digital settings, can contribute to tooth displacement outside the alveolar bone or undesirable dental effects [32].

Panoramic radiography is the most common imaging method used in dentistry for dental screening and decision-making [37]. At the same time, panoramic images are difficult to analyze due to the large amount of information (in particular, dental and skeletal pathology, abnormalities and damage to periodontal tissues), as well as the overlap of various anatomical structures, which affects the image quality. In this case, artificial intelligence can be an important support for dentists [38]. In the literature, deep learning has been used mainly for the diagnosis and analysis of dentition series, as the detection of pathological conditions is more complex and likely requires more model training to improve results [39]. Various automated models have been created to analyze panoramic radiographs to identify, segment, and distinguish teeth according to dentition (permanent or primary), quadrant (upper, lower, left, right), and category (incisor, canine, premolar, molar) [40].

The modern desire of dental practices to increase the effectiveness of treatment has led to the development of numerous tools to achieve this, such as Dental Monitoring (DM) software [41].

Dental Monitoring is a combination of artificial intelligence and telemedicine that provides easy daily collaboration and communication between the dental clinic and the patient through smartphone software. The use of DM facilitates the coordination and execution of each step and the monitoring of the goals achieved throughout the treatment period. Due to the advantages of using this tool by both the doctor and the patient, the demand for health applications is growing not only in

orthodontics but also in other medical specialties [42]. Current studies have shown that telemedicine also improves the accessibility of primary care, as it can reduce the time to get a consultation from a specialist, reduce the number of visits and waiting time, and allow for a faster response to emergencies [43].

Unlike other telecommunication systems, such as Skype, Google Duo, Zoom, and others [44], which cannot provide a standardized assessment of the clinical situation, the DM system provides automation of the process using deep learning algorithms [45].

Dalessandri D. et al. (2021) studied the approach of patients and dentists to the DM system during orthodontic treatment. The collected data showed that all dentists evaluated telemonitoring positively, as this method reduces the number of visits to the clinic. In addition, 96.25% of them considered it a source of high-tech and high-quality treatment. In addition, 97.5% of respondents rated telemonitoring positively; 81.25% considered telemonitoring an indicator of high-tech treatment, and the same 81.25% expressed their interest in reducing the number of visits to the office [46].

The study by Impellizzeri A. et al. (2020) shows that the use of DM with CuNiTi arches 0.014×0.025 in orthodontic treatment with a self-ligating bracket system using the straight arch technique successfully reduced the number of appointments for each patient from three to two in 10 weeks of work. In this regard, there was a reduction in the time of use of the dental chair in the office and a decrease in the material costs of the clinic, and the assessment of the treatment course by the doctor became more accurate and faster [47].

Conclusions.

Artificial intelligence is one of the most promising work tools due to its high accuracy and efficiency. Given the current scientific dynamics in the field of AI, it can be assumed that it will become an integral part of diagnosis and treatment planning in the near future. Practicing dentists will be able to use it as an additional tool to reduce their workload and improve the accuracy of diagnosis, decision-making, treatment planning, and prediction of outcomes. However, this requires close cooperation between the developers of commercial AI products and the scientific community to provide practitioners with an adequate diagnostic assessment to make reliable and informed therapeutic decisions. Further research, including randomized clinical trials, is needed to prove the value of this concept in dental practice to provide highly effective dental care and optimal treatment options for patients.

Modern artificial intelligence is very good at utilizing structured knowledge and gaining insights from large amounts of data. However, it is not able to create associations as the human brain does, and is only partially capable of making complex decisions in a clinical situation. In turn, the effectiveness of AI is achieved only when unbiased training data and a properly designed and trained algorithm are used.

The application of artificial intelligence in orthodontics is very close to being used by the general public, and the areas of application in the practice of a doctor are the most diverse. The development of AI solutions for various clinical problems facilitates the work

of doctors. Artificial intelligence has the potential to revolutionize medicine and dentistry in particular.

There is no conflict of interest.

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